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Leadership Styles of Deans/heads and Employees' Workplace well-being of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region, Philippines

Damianus Abun¹, Egdonna A. Quinto², Theogenia Magallanes³, Mary Joy Encarnacion⁴, Nathanael Flores⁵

^{1,2,4}Divine Word College of Laoag, Ilocos Norte, Philippines, ^{3,5}St. Benedict College of Northern Luzon, Ilocos Sur, Philippines

frdamy@yahoo.com

Abstract. The study wanted to determine the correlation between leadership styles of deans/heads and employees' workplace well-being. To support the theory of the study, the related literature was reviewed. The population of the study was the employees and the heads of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The study applied the correlational research design and the data were gathered using questionnaires. It used the descriptive and inferential statistics to interpret the data and weighted mean was used to determine the level of leadership styles and workplace well-being and Pearson r Product moment of Correlation was used to determine the correlation between the variables. The study found that the four leadership styles of deans were at a moderate level and there is a correlation between leadership styles of deans/head and the workplace well-being of employees. Therefore the hypothesis of the study is accepted.

Keywords. Leadership styles, workplace well-being, job satisfaction, employer care, autonomy, relatedness, competence

I. Introduction

The performance of a certain company or a certain school cannot be just attributed to the financial capability of the company or the school. Though it is still recognized as an important contributing factor to growth and performance it cannot also ignore the role of managerial leadership in contributing to the growth. Studies have shown that leadership is one of the contributing factors to the performance of employees. For example, Asrar-ul-Haq and Kuchinke (2016) studied the effect of transformational leadership, transactional, and laissez-faire leadership styles toward employees' job performance in the banking sector. The study found that each leadership styles contribute to a certain degree of the job performance of employees. Different leadership styles affect the motivation to work and consequently, it affects the output of their work or performance. Take the example of the study of Apak and Gumus (2015). They studied the effect of different leadership styles of administrators on the motivation and performance of employees and they found that leadership styles affect the motivation and performance of employees.

Work motivation and performance cannot also be separated from the workplace well-being of employees. Good workplace well-being increases work motivation and consequently, it

contributes to the work engagement of employees. Providing a good workplace is the role of leadership. Abun (2020) confirmed in his study that giving attention to the workplace well-being such as care, no intrusion of work into private life, autonomy need, competency need, relatedness need correlates to the work engagement of employees.

Based on the above finding, the current study would like to find out if there is a correlation between the exercises of different leadership styles and the well-being of employees. Many studies have been conducted related to leadership styles and job satisfaction and performance such as Nidadhavolu, (2018), Korkmaz, (2007), Elmore (2004), and many more. The current researcher has not found any researches that investigate the leadership styles and workplace well-being of employees. Therefore, the current research is intended to see if the practice of certain leadership styles affect the workplace well-being of employees or not.

II. Related Literature Review

A literature review is a comprehensive summary of the previous books and researches related to the current research. The previous literature would give a clear theoretical foundation for the present study (Bloomsburg University, n.d). Thus, this part is reviewing different works of literature and studies related to different theories and studies of leadership and its effect on job satisfaction and performance. Some leadership theories will be presented as the basis for the investigation.

Servant Leadership

Servant leadership is proposed by Robert K. Greenleaf (Spears, 1996). He initiated the servant leadership movement. The practice of servant leadership is nothing new because it was the leadership style of Jesus Christ. He came to serve and not to be served as Garr (2003) argued that servant leadership is restoring the Jesus Model but it was Greenleaf that coined the term, “the servant as leader”. In such term, it is the word “servant” comes first before the word, “leader”. From such a word, we can have an idea about the main focus of servant leaders. Thus, a servant leader is “the servant first...it begins with the natural feeling that one wants to serve, to serve first” (Greenleaf as cited by Rober. K. Greenleaf Centre for Servant Leadership, n.d). Therefore the focus of servant leadership is more on others first than upon self and the role of a servant leader is to serve. The primary objective and the prime motivation for leadership is to serve and meet the needs of others. Self-interest should not motivate servant leadership rather it should ascend to a higher plane of motivation. In line with this concept, thus the primary concern of leadership is to help people grow and flourish (Stone and Rushell, 2003 cited from Greenleaf, 1977).

Reading the concept of servant leadership is similar to the concept of transformational leadership styles. But stone and Rushell (2003) argued that though the two concepts are similar to each other but the focus is different. On one hand, the focus of servant leadership is the followers and the accomplishment of organizational outcomes or the subordinate outcome is the secondary. On the other hand, the prime objective of transformational leadership is the attainment of organizational objectives. Therefore building followers’ commitment toward the attainment of organizational objectives is the main agenda. This can be done through empowerment. In other words, servant leader values more on people who constitute the organization than the organization. In this case, running after profit is not his/her main concern but the real point of business is to serve. He/she does not serve with a focus on the result but rather focus on the service itself. Therefore, the primary responsibility is to build a relationship and people, and these take precedence over the task and product (Harvey, 2001).

According to Liden, et.al (2008) there are several dimensions of servant leadership and these are emotional healing, creating value for the community, conceptual skills, empowerment, helping subordinates to grow and succeed, putting others first, and ethical behavior. Emotional healing means that leaders help employees with their problems and care about their well-being. Meanwhile, creating value for the community refers to the efforts of leaders to give back to the community, helping people in the community and involved in community activities. Further, leaders also should have conceptual skills in which leaders can tell if something is wrong, think through complex problems, and has a thorough understanding of the organization. Beyond conceptual skills, leaders should have the capacity and skills to empower their subordinates which means that leaders give subordinates the power to make decisions, encourages subordinates to handle problems on their own, and gives subordinates to handle difficult situations. They have also the capacity to help subordinates grow in the sense that they provide career development paths for their subordinates, make sure that their subordinates reach their career goals, and help subordinates to develop new skills. Besides, leaders also can put others before themselves in which leaders care more about others, prioritizes the other's best interests over his/her own, and sacrifice his/her interest to meet other's needs. Lastly, servant leaders have the ethical behaviors in which leaders should have high ethical standards, are always honest, and should not compromise ethical principles.

Charismatic Leadership

The charismatic leadership concept was developed by Max Weber, a German Sociologist. It is the power to lead followers through their personality and special abilities in communication, and their special capabilities to communicate to their followers on an emotional level (Riggio, 2014). Leaders use norms to build a strong emotional relationship with their followers who work for them, not to inspire allegiance of followers to the institution. In this case, they convince followers to work not through authority as autocratic leaders do but through their appeal by being sensitive to followers' emotional needs and building a social and emotional relationship with them. They appeal to the emotions of their followers or audience. Therefore, the power is partly emanated from the special qualities or character of the person as Wiseman cited by Cohen (2012) argued that 50% of charisma is innate and 50% is trained. Authority is originated from his/her charisma. The power to influence is not emanated from the position which is emanated from the law attached to a particular office or position. It owes nothing to a person's status, social position, or status but more to the personality of the person who is exercising the leadership role.

As we have mentioned above that charismatic leadership is innate and at the same time is trained which means that charismatic leadership can be learned. This idea is an old one since ever since researchers and leadership experts such as Arvey, et.al (2007) have been arguing that some traits of leadership are innate but mostly are made. In the sense that there are inborn characteristics and these are considered raw materials that can be built upon to be a leader. Traits like assertiveness, extroversion, risk-taker, intelligence, and empathy are examples of important characters that need to be possessed by a leader to be effective. They are considered innate because they either you have it or you don't have it (Riggio, 2014). They seem to possess some magical qualities that others do not have. They possess some sort of gift given by God. However, growing evidence also shows that people can become more charismatic because some elements are charisma (gift) which are inborn and some elements are behavior that is acquired, developed, and honed over time through experience (Riggio, 2014). Besides the traits, it has been accepted that leadership is developed through experience. The same truth is with

charismatic leadership. Therefore education and training development is important to develop people to become a leader.

Conger and Kanungo (1989) identified several behavioral dimensions of a charismatic leader and these are strategic vision and articulation, sensitivity to the environment, sensitivity to member needs, personal risk, and unconventional behavior. In the first place, a charismatic leader provides an inspiring strategic vision of the organization, being able to generate new ideas for the future of the organization, brings up ideas about future possibilities. Second place, a charismatic leader can read and recognize what is going on in the environment that may block or facilitate achieving the goals, recognize constraints in the social and cultural environment that may hinder the attainment of organizational goals, and recognize members' capability to carry out the vision and mission of the organization. The third is his/her sensitivity to members' needs. He/she can read the needs and feel what others feel and express personal concern for the needs and feelings of other members of the organization. Fourth is a risk-taker. He/she can take a personal risk for the sake of the organization and sacrifice personal cost for the organization and is willing to engage in activities involving considerable self-sacrifice. The fifth is unconventional behavior in which he/she is engaging in unconventional or non-traditional behavior to achieve organizational goals or exhibiting unique behavior that surprises members of the organization.

Transactional Leadership

Transactional leadership is a leadership style in which a leader provide carrot and stick to influence his followers or employees to work. Providing a better reward and punishment will motivate employees to exert effort to perform well in their job (Silins, 1993, Cherry, 2019). Beyond reward and punishment, this kind of leadership is also accompanied by several strategies such as chain of command is clear, clear instruction from the leader on the goals to be achieved, and monitoring to ensure the expected goals are achieved. Consequently, this kind of leadership relies heavily on the team's compliance with the rules, instructions, and expectations that have been made clear to the employees or followers and carry out punishment when employees fail to follow rules and meet the expectations are key to the attainment of the goals.

Based on the above concept, we may argue that transactional leadership focuses on the means on how to achieve the goals of the organization, unlike transformational leadership which focuses on the ends. A transactional leader negotiates and bargains over the means as Pillai, et.al (1999) argued that transactional leadership is based on the exchange process in which the leader provides rewards in exchange for a good performance. The employers have to specify reward and punishment when the employees reach the expectations and punishment when they fail to achieve what is expected. Therefore, the employer has to spell out what is expected from the employees related to his/her job and specify the pay that the employee is going to receive from doing the job. The relationship between employer and employees is transactional because the relationship is based on economic exchange, equitable exchange. The authority is based on an economic exchange (Abun, 2004). The employer promises something to the employees when they perform their job and they will be punished when performing poorly. Therefore rules, procedures, performance standards are primary components of transactional leadership.

To ensure that the expectations will be met, the employer has to monitor the employees' work to see to it that they are on the right track. Bass (1990) argued that leaders need to watch the work of the employees to see deviations from rules and takes corrective measures. Therefore, the purpose of monitoring is to ensure that errors are detected as early as possible and interventions should be implemented as early as possible (Bass, 1990). One of the tools in the

monitoring of performance is performance evaluation which can be done quarterly or annually depending on the policy of certain companies or organizations. Through the performance evaluation, the employer can see if the employees are following the rules and carrying out their duties and responsibilities as expected (Asiimwe, et.al, 2016).

Transformational leadership

Transformational leadership was conceptualized by Burns (1978). Transformational leadership does not describe specific sets of behaviors of leaders but rather it is a concept that views leadership as a process in which leaders and followers raise one another to a higher level of morality and motivation. Leaders focus on efforts that will inspire their followers to reach higher ideals and moral values such as justice, and equality. This makes the difference between transformational and transactional leadership. Transactional leadership focuses on followers' self-interest or higher needs, while transformational leadership motivates their followers by appealing to strong emotion regardless of the ultimate effect on the followers. Leaders look for potential motives in followers and seek to satisfy higher needs (self-actualization) and engage the full person of the follower, not only intellectually but also morally (Bass, 1985) and this effort will help the followers to attain their better self as a person. That is the essence of transformational leadership in which leaders and followers engage each other in such a way that leaders and followers raise one another to a higher level of motivation and morality (Burns, 1978). They lift each other into their better self and managers find satisfaction from helping their followers or employees to grow becoming better persons and a leader. They find personal interest in helping their staff to be better because witnessing the growth and development of their people give them great pleasure or joy.

Based on the concept that we have presented earlier, one can see the unique characteristics of transformational leadership that leaders do not focus on the past but they focus on the present situation of employees, and based on the present situation of employees they focus on the future of employees particularly on what they can become. Thus they perceive reality and potentiality or actuality and potentiality. Therefore, they confirm individuals based on what they are and what they might become. They find joy in helping to convert potentiality into actuality, to become what might become (Brubacher, et.al, 1994). To do that, they do not impose things on the employees on what to be done to develop themselves but they engage the full person of the employees. In this case, they are not treated as an object to be manipulated but they are subjects, persons with dignity who participate in developing themselves and this are done through motivation and inspiration (Whitetaker, et.al, 2009) and empowerment (Burns, 1978). In this case, the leader acts as a facilitator or coach in developing their employees.

To develop employees, the leaders identify the values and motives of their followers and appeal to these values and motives. They are taking a personal interest in developing them. By taking the personal interest of each of his/her employees, the transformational leaders get to know them as individual persons. This knowledge includes knowledge about who their employees are today and what they want to be in the future, knowledge on employees' basic values, and their principal motivators – what spurs them to act. In other words, leaders know their dreams, values, and their principles and elevate these dreams and values to a higher level. It is just like what Abraham Maslow's hierarchical needs in which the leaders try to elevate the motivation of employees from physiological to psychological, then to safety- to belongingness- to self-esteem, and finally to self-actualization. A transformational leader is facilitating the movement of each person up the hierarchy and as a consequence of each advancement, new values and motives emerge (Leithwood, 1992).

To summarize the above ideas, Bass and Steidlmeier (1998) presented four dimensions of transformational leadership and these are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized considerations. A leader is known to be transformational when he has charisma or idealized influence in which he/she can make others feel good working with him, make others look up to him as a model, set high standards for emulation, project moral values to his followers. Besides charisma, a leader has inspirational motivation in the sense that he/she provides followers with challenges and meaning for engaging in shared goals and undertakings, articulates a compelling vision for the future, and helps followers to find meaning in the work. Whereas its intellectual stimulation means that a leader can open the mind of his/her followers to question old assumptions, beliefs, and practices. The leaders involve the followers or employees in generating solutions to problems and open the mind of others/followers with new ways of looking at problems. In terms of its individualized considerations, it requires a leader to treat followers individually and provide coaching, mentoring, and growth opportunities according to individual needs.

Workplace Well-Being

The ideas on workplace well-being presented in this study follow my previous ideas (Abun, 2020) on workplace well-being discussion. I have published the paper in the International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science. I have argued that there has been growing attention in investigating the cause of job performance, job engagement, and job satisfaction. To increase job performance, managers have been searching for ways on how to increase job satisfaction and work engagement. Thus, managers must identify the elements or variables that contribute to job performance. Along this line, it has been identified that one of the elements that promote job performance is workplace well-being. Well-being encompasses factors that affect the lives of employees in their workplace. Those factors may include their job satisfaction, their relationship with peers and management, employer care, employee autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Black Dog Institute (n.d) particularly identifies several variables that are considered to be the elements of workplace well-being and these are work satisfaction, organizational respect for the employee, employer care, and intrusion of work into private life. The variables were identified after it has conducted a study on workplace well-being and the variables were based on self-reported areas of workplace well-being identified by the employees themselves. Like Black Dog Institute's variables, the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) of Deci and Ryan (2000) has presented several validated variables that contribute to workplace well-being of employees such as autonomy (deCharms, 1968), relatedness (Baumeister, & Leary, 1995) and competence (Harter, 1978). These are three basic psychological needs and these needs are innate. These three needs are called intrinsic motivational needs and they are important in improving the workplace well-being of employees. Deci and Ryan (2000) argued that the workplace environment must be supportive of the growth of these needs to create a healthy workplace environment and the well-being of employees.

To guide our direction in this paper, we need to elaborate further on different variables that are identified by the Black Dog Institute and Self-Determination Theory (SDT) of Ryan and Deci (2000) which are considered to contribute to the workplace well-being and these are job satisfaction, organizational respect, employer care, no intrusion of work into private life, autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Job satisfaction well-being means that employees find fulfillment in their work, a sense of direction and meaning, a sense of satisfaction, and increase their self-worth and offer challenges. While well-being in terms of organizational respect indicate that organization members respect and trust one another and member believe the worth

of the organization. Whereas employer care means that the leadership lend their ears to employees' concerns, feel emphatic toward their employees, treat employees as they wanted to be treated, share the burdens of employees and care about the well-being of their employees. Meanwhile, no intrusion into private life requires that employees' work should not take the time of their private life. Ryan and Deci (2000) added that beyond job satisfaction, organizational respect, and no intrusion of work into private life, employees' need for autonomy has to be given attention. In this case, an organization has to see to it that freedom is guaranteed. Besides, the organization provides an environment in which the employees can relate to one another and care for one another. Lastly, the organization sees to it that their competence needs should not be neglected which means that they have the efficacy and skills to perform their work.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Simply Psychology (n.d)

Figure 1: The framework reflects the correlation between the independent and dependent variables. Independent variables are the control variables that can be manipulated or changed to affect the dependent variables (Simply Psychology, n.d). Dependent variables are changed when the independent variables are changed. These variables are dependent on the independent variables. In this study, leadership styles of Deans are independent variables, and the workplace well-being of employees and dependent variables.

Statement of the Problems

The object of the study is to determine the correlation between the different leadership styles of Deans of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region and workplace well-being of employees, particularly to answer the following questions:

1. What is the leadership styles of Deans of Divine word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of
 - a. Servant leadership
 - b. Charismatic leadership
 - c. Transactional leadership
 - d. Transformational leadership
2. What is the workplace well-being of employees in terms of
 - a. Job satisfaction
 - b. Organizational respect
 - c. Employer care
 - d. No intrusion of work into private life
 - e. Autonomy needs
 - f. Relatedness need
 - g. Competence need
3. Is there a relationship between different leadership styles of Deans and workplace well-being variables?

Assumption

The study believes that using a proper leadership style can influence the workplace well-being of employees and can be measured. The study also assumes that the questionnaires are valid and the answers are objective.

Hypothesis

Basit, et.al (2018) found that applying different leadership styles affect different degrees of job performance. Base on the theory, the current study hypothesizes that the leadership styles of Deans correlate to the workplace well-being of employees.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study is conducted only to the Deans and employees of Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Region, Ilocos Sur, and Ilocos Norte. Leadership styles to be assessed are servant leadership styles, charismatic leadership styles, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership. Concerning workplace well-being, it is limited to job satisfaction, organizational respect, employer care, no intrusion of work into private life, autonomy needs, relatedness need, and competency needs.

III. Research Methodology

The research methodology is the procedures or techniques to select, identify, process, and analyze information about the topic. The research methodology determines the validity, reliability, and quality of a certain study (Wilkinson & Birmingham, 2003). Thus, the study was carried out through appropriate research methodologies such as research design, data gathering instruments, population, the locale of the study, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

Since the study is a quantitative research and therefore it used descriptive assessment and correlational research design to determine the level of different leadership styles of Deans and its effect on the workplace well-being of employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The nature of descriptive research is to describe what is found in the data collected through questionnaires and statistical treatment. It is also used to describe profiles, frequency distribution, describe characteristics of people, situation, phenomena, or relationship variables. In short, it describes “what is” about the data (Ariola, 2006, cited by Abun, 2019).

In line with the current study, the descriptive assessment and correlational method were deployed. The study determines the level of different leadership styles and their effect on workplace well-being. This was to determine what the dominant leadership styles deans were and to what extent it affects the workplace well-being of employees.

The locale of the Study

The locale of the study was Divine Word Colleges in Ilocos Sur and Ilocos Norte.

Population

The population of the study was composed of all employees and faculty of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region. The total enumeration sampling was used and 250 faculty and employees were taken as respondents of the study.

Data Gathering instruments

The study adapted validated questionnaires of Multifactor Leadership Questionnaires (MLQ) that were made by Avolio, et.al (1995), Conger, and Kanungo (1994) of 5-Steps-Scale of Charismatic Leadership, and Liden, Wayne, Zhao, and Henderson’s (2008) Multidimensional Measure and Multi-level Assessment Servant Leadership.

Data Gathering Procedures

In the process of data gathering, the researcher sent letters to the President of the Colleges, requesting them to allow the researcher to flow his questionnaires in the college. The researcher personally met the Presidents and employees and requested them to answer the questionnaires. The retrieval of questionnaires was arranged between the President’s representative and the researcher with the help of employees and faculty of the college.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In consistence with the descriptive assessment and descriptive correlational research design, therefore descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used. The weighted mean is used to determine the level of different leadership styles of deans and the Pearson r was used to measure the correlation of different leadership styles toward the workplace well-being of employees.

The following ranges of values with their descriptive interpretation will be used:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Interpretation	Overall Descriptive Rating
4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

IV. Empirical Data and Analysis

Empirical data and analysis are evidence-based approached or data-driven information to analyze and interpret the data. It relies on real-world data rather than theories or concepts (Angelov & Principe, 2016). Based on this concept, the following are data that were gathered through research questionnaires and presented in the table forms according to the statement of the problems.

Problem 1: What is the leadership styles of Deans of Divine word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of

- e. *Servant leadership*
- f. *Charismatic leadership*
- g. *Transactional leadership*
- h. *Transformational leadership*
- i.

Table 1a. The Leadership Styles of Deans of Divine word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Servant leadership

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Employees/faculty would seek help from him if they have personal problems.	3.27	SWA
2. He/she cares about employees' well-being.	3.25	SWA
3. He/she emphasizes the importance of giving back to the community.	3.29	SWA
4. He/she is interested in helping people in the community.	3.23	SWA
5. He/she can tell if something goes wrong.	3.12	SWA
6. He/she has a thorough understanding of the organization and its goals.	3.19	SWA
7. He/she gives employees the responsibility to make decisions about their job.	3.21	SWA
8. He/she encourages others to handle important work decisions on their own.	3.17	SWA
9. He/she makes a career development plan for employees.	3.19	SWA
10. He/she makes sure that his employees reach their goals.	3.15	SWA
11. He/she cares more about employees' success than his own.	3.07	SWA
12. He/she puts others' best interest above his/her own.	3.06	SWA
13. He/she holds high ethical standards.	3.19	SWA
14. He/she is always honest.	3.17	SWA
Composite Mean	3.18	SWA

Source: Liden, Wayne, Zhao, and Henderson's (2008)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

As gleaned from the data on the table, it shows that as a whole, servant leadership of deans, heads is 3.18 which is considered as somewhat agree or moderate extent. It indicates that their servant leadership is not high or very high or it is not also low or very low. This result may not indicate a good indication of Catholic institutions which is supposed to be driven by the leadership of Jesus Christ which is servant leadership. The evaluation is consistent in all items

and all are evaluated as somewhat agree or moderate extent such as helping employees when they personal problems (3.27), caring for employees' well-being (3.25), giving back to the community (3.29), helping people in the community (3.23), tell the employees when something goes wrong (3.12), understanding the organizational goals (3.19), giving the employees the authority to make decisions about their job (3.21), encouraging his/her subordinates to handle important work decisions on their own (3.17), making career development plan for he/his employees (3.19), making sure his/her employees reach their goals (3.15), care more about employees' success than her/his own (3.07), putting the interest of her/his employees' interest above his/her own (3.06), holding high ethical standards (3.19), and are always honest (3.17).

Based on those findings, it alarms the management or the deans/heads to improve their servant leadership by looking into the specific areas of weakness to be improved.

Table 1b. The Leadership Styles of Deans of Divine word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Charismatic leadership

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. Has a vision and often brings up ideas about possibilities for the future.	3.33	SWA
2. He/she is a good public speaker.	3.32	SWA
3. He/she generates new ideas for the future of the organization.	3.23	SWA
4. He/she recognizes constraints in the physical environment (technological limitations, lack of resources/facilities) that may in the way of achieving organizational goals.	3.19	SWA
5. He/she Recognizes the abilities and skills of other members of the organization.	3.17	SWA
6. He/she can influence others by developing mutual liking and respect.	3.17	SWA
7. He/she shows sensitivity for the needs and feelings of other members of the organization.	3.18	SWA
8. He/she takes a high personal risk for the sake of the organization.	3.18	SWA
9. He/she often engages in activities involving considerable self-sacrifice for the organization.	3.17	SWA
10. He/she engages in unconventional behavior to achieve organizational goals.	3.14	SWA
11. He/she uses non-traditional means to achieve organizational goals.	3.14	SWA
Composite Mean	3.20	SWA

Source: Conger, and Kanungo (1994)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

As it is shown on the table, it reveals that as a whole, Charismatic leadership of deans/heads is 3.20 which is understood as somewhat agree or to a moderate extent. Such evaluation points out that the Charismatic leadership of deans/heads are not high or very high and are not also low or very low. Such assessment is consistent in all items singled out under charismatic leadership such as having a vision and often brings up ideas about possibilities for the future

(3.33), having public speaking capability (3.32), generating new ideas for the future of the organization (3.23), recognizing constraints in the physical environment (technological limitations, lack of resources/facilities) that may block the way to achieve the organizational goals (3.19), recognizing the abilities and skills of other members of the organization (3.17), influencing others by developing mutual liking and respect (3.17), showing sensitivity for the needs and feelings of other members of the organization (3.18), taking a high personal risk for the sake of the organization (3.18), engaging in activities involving considerable self-sacrifice for the organization (3.17), engaging in unconventional behavior to achieve organizational goals (3.14), and using non-traditional means to achieve organizational goals (3.14).

These findings remind the deans/heads to improve their charismatic leadership styles by improving the areas of weaknesses of their charismatic leadership.

Table 1c: The Leadership Styles of Deans of Divine word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Transactional leadership

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. He/she tells subordinates what to do if they want to be rewarded for their work.	3.25	SWA
2. He/she provides recognition/rewards when others reach their goals.	3.31	SWA
3. He/she is satisfied when employees/subordinates meet the agreed-upon goals.	3.31	SWA
4. He/she tells employees/subordinates the standards that they have to know to carry out their work.	3.37	SWA
Composite Mean	3.31	SWA

Source: Liden, Wayne, Zhao, and Henderson's (2008)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Concerning transactional leadership style, as a whole, it appears that the transactional leadership style of deans/heads is 3.31 which means that employees somewhat agree on the level of the transactional leadership style of their deans/heads. The evaluation indicates that the transactional leadership of deans/heads are not high or very high and are not low or very low. The evaluation is consistent in all items such as telling subordinates what to do if they want to be rewarded for their work (3.25), providing recognition/rewards when others reach their goals (3.31), being satisfied when employees/subordinates meet the agreed-upon goals (3.31) and telling employees/subordinates the standards that they have to know to carry out their work (3.37).

This evaluation is providing information for the deans/heads to improve their transactional leadership by looking into areas of weaknesses to be improved.

Table 1d: The Leadership Styles of Deans of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Transformational leadership

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. He/she makes others feel good to work with him.	3.05	SWA
2. Others are proud to be associated with him/her.	3.01	SWA
3. He/she talks about his most important values and belief to his/her employees.	2.99	SWA
4. He/she encourages employees to make the most of their real skills and capacities to their job.	2.99	SWA
5. He/she articulates a compelling vision for the future of the organization.	2.99	SWA
6. He/she enables employees to think about old problems in new ways.	2.94	SWA
7. He provides employees with new ways of looking at problems.	2.95	SWA
8. He/she employs to rethink ideas that they had never questioned before.	2.91	SWA
9. He/she is interested to know individual employee's difficulties.	2.94	SWA
10. He/she gives personal attention to employees who seem rejected.	2.91	SWA
11. He/she gives attention to the working conditions of his/her employees.	2.93	SWA
Composite Mean	2.96	SWA

Source: Avolio, et.al (1995)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Based on the data presented on the table, it manifests that as a whole transformational leadership of deans/heads gained a composite mean of 2.96 which can be understood as somewhat agree or a moderate extent. This assessment concludes that the transformational leadership styles of deans/heads are not high or very high and are not also low or very low. Even when the items are taken singly, all are within the same level of assessment such as making others feel good to work with him (3.05), making others feel proud to be associated with him/her (3.01), talking about his most important values and belief to his/her employees (2.99), encouraging employees to make the most of their real skills and capacities to their job (2.99), articulating a compelling vision for the future of the organization (2.99), enabling employees to think about old problems in new ways (2.94), providing employees with new ways of looking at problems (2.95), employing a strategy to rethink ideas that they had never questioned before (2.91), having the interest to know individual employee's difficulties (2.94), giving personal attention to employees who seem rejected (2.91), and giving attention to the working conditions of his/her employees (2.93).

Based on the finding, it shows that among all leadership styles measured, transformational leadership styles is the lowest. This suggests that the deans and heads must improve their transformational leadership styles by paying attention to the areas of weaknesses of their transformational leadership style.

Table 1e. Summary of the Leadership Style of Deans of Divine Word College in the Ilocos Region

ITEMS	Mean	DR
1. Servant Leadership	3.18	SWA
2. Charismatic Leadership	3.20	SWA
3. Transactional Leadership	3.31	SWA
4. Transformational leadership	2.96	SWA
Overall Mean	3.16	SWA

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In a summary, as manifested on the table, as a whole, the leadership styles of deans/heads got a 3.16 composite mean which means that employees somewhat agree with the level of the leadership styles of their deans/heads. It indicates that the leadership styles of deans/heads are not high or very high and are not low or very low. Even in all dimensions of leadership styles, all the deans/heads have the same level of evaluation which is somewhat agreed or a moderate extent. This concludes that deans and heads must improve their leadership styles.

Problem 2: What is the workplace well-being of employees in terms of

- a. Job satisfaction
- b. Organizational respect
- c. Employer care,
- d. No intrusion of work into private life
- e. Autonomy needs
- f. Relatedness needs
- g. Competence need

Table 2a. The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Job Satisfaction

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. My work is fulfilling.	3.79	A
2. My daily activities are giving meaning to my life.	3.80	A
3. My work brings a sense of satisfaction.	3.79	A
4. My work increases a sense of self-worth.	3.81	A
5. My work offer challenges to advance my skills.	3.86	A
Composite Mean	3.81	A

Source: Black Dog Institution (n.d).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Based on the result of the data, as a whole, the employees got a composite mean of 3.81 which means that the employees agree that they are satisfied with their job. In this case, their job satisfaction is not very high but high and is not low or very low. Even when the indicators are taken singly, all the indicators are evaluated within the same range of evaluation which is high or agrees such as their work is fulfilling (3.79), their daily activities are giving meaning to their life (3.80), their work brings a sense of satisfaction (3.79), their work increases a sense of self-worth (3.81), and their work offers challenges to advance their skills (3.86).

Even though the evaluation is high but there is still room for improvement on job satisfaction because the employees did not get very high job satisfaction.

Table2b. The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Organizational Respect

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I feel that there are trust and respect among employees and administrator.	3.19	SWA
2. I believe in the principles by which my employer operates.	3.29	SWA
3. I feel content with the way my employer treats its employees.	3.15	SWA
4. I feel that the employer respects staff.	3.26	SWA
5. People at my work believe in the worth of the organization.	3.33	SWA
Composite Mean	3.24	SWA

Source: Black Dog Institution (n.d)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

Looking into the data presented on the table, it makes plain that as a whole, the organizational respect gained a 3.24 composite mean which can be translated as somewhat agree or a moderate extent. This means that the employees perceive organizational respect is not high or very high and is not low or very low. Taking the indicators separately, they point out the same level of evaluation or assessment which is somewhat agreed or a moderate extent such as they feel that there are trust and respect among employees and administrators (3.19), believe in the principles by which their employer operates (3.29), feel content with the way their employer treats their employees (3.15), believe that the employer respects staff (3.26), and belief in the worth of the organization (3.33). The findings demonstrate a need for the improvement of organizational respect.

Table2c: The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Employer Care

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. At a difficult time, my boss is willing to lend an ear.	3.23	SWA
2. My boss is caring.	3.29	SWA
3. I feel that my boss is emphatic and understanding about my work concerns.	3.29	SWA
4. My boss treats me as I would like to be treated.	3.29	SWA
5. My boss shoulders some of my worries about work.	3.19	SWA
6. I believe that my employer cares about their staff's well-being.	3.15	SWA
Composite Mean	3.24	SWA

Source: Black Dog Institution (n.d)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

The same is true with employer care. As data displayed on the table, as a whole, it reveals that the employer care gained a composite mean of 3.24 which is understood as somewhat agree or a moderate extent. This shows that as a whole, the employer care is not high or very high and is not low or very low. Even though the indicators are taken separately, they still reveal the same evaluation which is somewhat agreed or a moderate extent such as their boss is willing to lend an ear during a difficult time (3.23), their boss is caring (3.29), their boss is emphatic and understanding about my work concerns (3.29), their boss treats them as they would like to be treated (3.29), their boss shoulders some of their worries about work (3.19), and they believe that their employer cares about their staff's well-being (3.15). These evaluations show a concern that employers need to pay attention to improve the situation.

Table 2d: The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of No Intrusion of Work into private Life

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. My work takes all my time including my private life.	2.69	SWA
2. I feel stressed in organizing my work time to meet demands.	2.63	SWA
3. I feel excessively pressured at work to meet targets and no time for myself.	2.69	SWA
4. After work, I find it hard to wind down.	2.67	SWA
5. I find myself thinking negatively about work outside office hours.	2.55	DA
Composite Mean	2.65	SWA

Source: Black Dog Institution (n.d).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

About the dimension of “no intrusion of work into their private life”, the data indicates that as a whole, “no intrusion of work into private life” gained a composite mean of 2.65 which means employees somewhat agree that there is no intrusion of work into their private life. However, the data shows that the “no intrusion of work into private life” is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low. It means that there is still a moderate extent of office work that enters their private life. Taking the items singly, it is also obvious that the evaluation is the same such as their work take their time including their private life (2.69), they feel stressed in organizing their work time to meet demands (2.63), feel excessively pressured at work to meet targets and no time for themselves (2.69), find it hard to wind down after work (2.67), however, they disagree that they find themselves thinking negatively about work outside office hours (2.55). This finding reveals a concern that work also enters the private life of employees to a moderate extent.

Table 2e: The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Autonomy Needs

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. At work, I feel a sense of choice and freedom in the things I undertake.	3.24	SWA
2. I feel that my decisions on my job reflect what I want.	3.44	A
3. I feel my choices on my job express who really, I am.	3.42	A
4. I feel I have been doing what interests me in my job.	3.45	A
Composite Mean	3.39	SWA

Source: Deci and Ryan (2000)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In terms of autonomy needs, the data also pointed out the same range of evaluation. As a whole, the data displays a composite mean of 3.39 which can be interpreted as somewhat agree or a moderate extent. This indicates that the fulfillment of the autonomy need is not high or very high and it is not also low or very low. The evaluation reveals a concern to be given attention by the management to provide an environment where the employees can realize their autonomy need. However, when the items are taken separately, they reveal mixed evaluation within the range of “agree or high” such as “feeling that their decision on their job reflect what they want (3.44), feeling their choices on my job express who really, they are (3.42), feeling that they have been doing what interests them in their job (3.45) and the employees somewhat agree that they feel a sense of choice and freedom in the things they undertake” (3.24).

Table 2f: The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Relatedness Needs

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I feel that the people I care at work about also care about me.	3.50	SWA
2. I feel connected with people who care for me at work and for whom I care at work.	3.57	A
3. At work, I feel close and connected with other people who are important to me.	3.57	A
4. I experience a warm feeling with the people I spend time with at work.	3.65	A
Composite Mean	3.57	A

Source: Deci and Ryan (2000)

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In contrary to the autonomy need, the evaluation of relatedness need is different. As gleaned from the data, it displays that as a whole, relatedness need achieved a composite mean of 3.57 which means that the employees agree that their relatedness need is fulfilled. However, such an evaluation is not also very high which indicates room for improvement. Taking the items separately, the evaluation also falls within the same range of evaluation which is agreed or high such as “feeling that the people they care at work about also care about me (3.50), feeling connected with people who care for them at work and for whom they care at work (3.57), feeling close and connected with other people who are important to them (3.57), and experiencing a warm feeling with the people they spend time with at work” (3.65).

Table 2g: The Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word Colleges in the Ilocos Region in terms of Competence Needs

INDICATORS	Mean	DR
1. I feel confident that I can do things well on my job.	3.66	A
2. At work, I feel capable of what I do.	3.64	A
3. When I am at work, I feel competent to achieve my goals.	3.61	A
4. In my job, I feel I can complete a difficult task.	3.60	A
Composite Mean	3.63	A

Source: Deci and Ryan (2000).

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Strongly agree	Very High
3.41-4.20	Agree	High
2.61-3.40	Somewhat agree	Moderate
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low/High
1.00-1.80	Strongly disagree	Very Low/Very High

In terms of competence need, it shows the same evaluation as the relatedness need. The tables reveal that as a whole, the competence needs obtained a composite mean of 3.63 which is also translated as "agree or high". Such evaluations point out that the realization of competence need is high but not very high which also recommends an improvement. Taking them separately, all items are also given the same level of evaluation which is "agree or high" such as "feeling confident that they can do things well on their job (3.66), feeling capable of what they do (3.64), feeling competent to achieve their goals (3.61), and feeling that they can complete the difficult task" (3.60).

Table 2h: Summary of Workplace well-being of Employees of Divine Word College in the Ilocos Region

Dimensions	MEAN	DR
a. Job satisfaction	3.81	A
b. Organizational respect	3.24	SWA
c. Employer care	3.24	SWA
d. No Intrusion of work into private life	2.65	SWA
e. Autonomy needs	3.39	SWA
f. Relatedness need	3.57	A
g. Competence need	3.63	A
Overall mean	3.36	SWA

In summary, the data reveals that as a whole employees' workplace well-being obtained an overall mean rating of 3.36 which is an indication of somewhat agree or a moderate extent. Overall, the workplace well-being of employees is not high or very high and is not also low or very low. It indicates that the employees' workplace well-being has not been highly or highly attained and therefore something can be done to improve the situation. Taking the dimensions separately, there is a mixed evaluation in which some dimensions are evaluated "somewhat agree or moderate extent" and some dimensions are evaluated as "agree or high" such as job satisfaction (3.81), relatedness need (3.57), competence need (3.63), but organizational respect (3.24), employer care (3.24), and no intrusion of work into private life (2.65) are somewhat agree or moderate extent.

Problem 3: Is there a relationship between different leadership styles of Deans and workplace well-being variables?

Table 3: Relationship between different leadership styles of Deans and workplace well-being variables

		Servant leadership	Charismatic Leadership	Transactional Leadership	Transformational
Job satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.489**	.527**	.283**	.485**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Organizational respect	Pearson Correlation	.743**	.630**	.478**	.613**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Employer care	Pearson Correlation	.813**	.756**	.555**	.701**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Pearson Correlation		.114	.117	.056	.161*

No Intrusion of work into private life	Sig. (2-tailed)	.164	.155	.499	.049
	N	150	150	150	150
Autonomy needs	Pearson Correlation	.598**	.591**	.353**	.560**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Relatedness need	Pearson Correlation	.496**	.501**	.427**	.399**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	150	150	150	150
Competence need	Pearson Correlation	.498**	.502**	.226**	.505**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.005	.000
	N	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Concerning the correlation between leadership styles of deans/heads and workplace well-being of employees, the Pearson r Product Moment of Correlation table indicates that there is a relationship between leadership styles of deans/head and workplace well-being of employees at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) of significance. Specifically, there is a relationship between servant leadership, charismatic leadership, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership and workplace well-being of employees particularly with job satisfaction, organizational respect, employer care, no intrusion of work into private life, autonomy needs, relatedness need, and competence need. But the Pearson r Product Moment of Correlation also indicates that among the four leadership styles measured in this study, it is the only transformational leadership style that is correlated to "no intrusion of work into private life", at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) of significance, while the other three leadership styles are not correlated to "no intrusion of work into private life".

V. Result and Discussion

The findings of the study indicate that leadership styles are contributing factors to the workplace well-being of employees. It suggests that changing or improving leadership styles can change or affect the well-being of employees. Maintaining the current and the same leadership style would mean the destruction of employees' well-being. Studies have found that workplace well-being is correlated with work performance (War & Nielsen, 2018, Haddon, 2018). In the school context, applying the right leadership styles can mean boosting faculty and employees' performance and therefore it can affect the quality of education.

The results of this study suggest that administrators need to revisit their leadership styles and take a step to improve their leadership styles. Failing to give attention to their leadership styles can destroy the workplace environment and further can damage the quality and the school's quality and reputation.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is a correlation between leadership styles of deans/heads and the workplace well-being of employees and therefore the hypothesis of the study is accepted. It means that the changes or improvements in leadership styles can improve employees' well-being.

The study also recognizes its limitation. This study does not cover all the Divine Word Colleges in the Philippines and therefore the result of this study may not represent the whole situation of Divine Word Colleges in the Philippines. Besides, there are many dimensions of workplace well-being that are covered by this study and therefore, there is a need to investigate in the

future study about a different aspect of workplace well-being such as hedonic workplace well-being and eudaimonic well-being.

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